

INFLUENCE ON THE MECHANICAL BEHAVIOR OF CARBON FIBER FABRIC REINFORCED PPS LAMINATES UNDER DIFFERENT TEMPERATURE

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, the influence of temperature on the mechanical behavior of carbon fiber fabric reinforced PPS laminates was investigated through the experimental method. In order to obtain the strength and the failure mechanisms of carbon fiber fabric reinforced PPS laminates under the different temperature, three different tests (tensile, compressive and flexural) were carried out at five temperature points (23°C、60°C、90°C、120°C and 150°C). The resulting experimental database is of the almost importance for generating design allowable for structure integrating such thermoplastic-based composites. It can be obtained that the viscoplastic behavior of the PPS resin can be enhanced with increase of temperature around its glass transition temperature ($T_g = 98^\circ\text{C}$). However, the interface intensity between the fiber/matrix will be reduced with increase of temperature. Therefore, the mechanical properties of the compressive and flexural will be also reduced with increase of temperature. Whereas the influence of temperature on the tensile modulus and tensile strength of carbon fiber fabric reinforced PPS laminates is small. From the microscopic observations it can be obtained that the influence of temperature on the failure mechanisms is obvious. Due to the softening of PPS resin with the temperature increasing higher than the glass transition temperature, the failure mode of carbon fiber fabric reinforced PPS laminates was changed at elevated temperature, particularly in the compressive test and flexural test.

1 INTRODUCTION

Thermosetting resin (referred to as TS in this paper)–based composite materials have been extensively used over the past 40 years. Even though they display useful mechanical properties, they also present undeniable drawbacks, such as the need for low-temperature storage, a hard-to-control reticulation process, a very long curing process, and handmade draping, which causes most of the irreversible defects of the manufacturing process. In such an environment, high-performance thermoplastic resins (referred to as TP) offer a promising alternative to TS resins. Indeed, TP resins offer a number of advantages over conventional TS resins, such as epoxies. Thermoplastics exhibit a high degree of chemical resistance, as well as excellent damage and impact resistance, and they may be used over a wide range of temperatures. They have a very low level of moisture uptake, and consequently, their mechanical properties are less degraded under hot/wet conditions. TP composite materials offer a number of advantages but also require different manufacturing and repair techniques. It is possible to produce TP-based laminates with complex shapes in few stages using a thermoforming process. In addition, unlike TS resins, TP resins may be melted down after they are formed, thus providing recycling possibilities. They may also be joined using a process called fusion bonding, allowing TP composites to be joined by heating them close to their melting point. However, TP composites are more difficult to repair than conventional TS-based composites, and high-performance

TP are more expensive. Thus, a wide range of TP resins are available, but in the area of high-performance TP resins, polyetheretherketone (PEEK) and polyphenylenesulfide (PPS) are probably the most widely investigated TP resins.^[1] At high temperature, the nonlinear behavior of fiber-reinforced composites becomes significant, especially under off-axis loading conditions.^[2,3] This nonlinear response, associated with the shear deformation of the polymer matrix along reinforcing fibers, is enhanced at elevated temperatures due to the viscoplastic nature of the TP matrix.^[4-6] The load-bearing performances of pin-connected unidirectional (UD) carbon/PPS composites have been evaluated at 21°C.^[7] There is no study currently available in the literature that investigates the joints' strength at elevated temperature for carbon fabric reinforced PPS. Thus, very few works highlight the behavior of carbon fabric PPS laminates^[8,9] and a few authors investigated the influence of high temperatures on the behavior of UD-reinforced PPS matrix.^[10-14]

2 MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1. Materials

The composite materials studied in this work are carbon fabrics reinforced PPS prepreg laminates plates supplied by the company Porcher and referenced as 3106-C3K PPS Pi preg. The woven plies prepreg laminate consists of 5-harness satin weave carbon fiber fabrics in a toughened PPS resin matrix (Fortron 0214 supplied by the company Ticona). The volume fraction of carbon fibers is 50% and the mass fraction is 57%. The carbon fibers fabrics whose reference is T300 3K 5HS are supplied by the company SOFICAR. The composite laminate is manufactured using the compression moulding technique, and the prepreg plates are hot pressed according to the same stacking sequence: [0/90]4s, the fabrics is balanced in warp and weft directions. The details of the 5-harness satin weave fabric are listed in Table 1. Even though the lay-up [0/90]4s is not suitable for use in aircraft structures, it allows the authors to investigate specifically the plastic accommodation mechanism in order to understand the specific contribution of TP matrix to the high temperature behavior of high-performance TP-based laminates.

Table 1 Satin weave carbon/PPS composite information

Carbon fiber type	T300 JB
TEX(g/km)	198
End/pick count, yarns per 10cm	70
Yarn filament count	3000
Filament diameter(mm)	0.007
Carbon fiber density(g/cm ³)	1.75
Fabric areal density(g/cm ²)	285
Overall fiber volume fraction	50±3%

2.2. Method

All the tests were performed using a 100-kN capacity load cell of an Instron 3369 testing machine at room moisture. The temperature control system, including an oven and a temperature controller, provide a stable temperature environment during the test. The operating temperature ranged from room temperature to 120 °C. A series of three tests were conducted on C/PPS laminates to get the mechanical properties of a C/PPS lamina: tensile, compressive and flexural tests. In these tests, the mechanical properties were determined according to the standards presented in Table 2. In the table, w and h denote the width and thickness of the specimen, respectively, and V represents constant crosshead speed (mm/min) applied to the specimen during displacement-controlled tests. Fractography analysis is commonly used to ascertain the failure mechanisms of thermoplastic laminates. A sweeping electronic microscope JEOL JSM-35CF was used to perform such analysis on failure surfaces after all the tests.

Table 2 Standards, specimen size and test conditions

Test	Standard	Specimen size	Test conditions
Tensile	ASTM D3039-07	230×25	V=0.5mm/min
Compressive	ASTM D6641-01	139.7×12.7	V=1mm/min
Flexural	ASTM D709-07	96×12.7	V=1mm/min

3 RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

3.1 Tensile test

These tests were conducted to investigate the role of matrix ductility, potentially enhanced by temperature, from these definitions, the stress-strain curves of the C/PPS laminates can be compared for these laminates at different temperature (Fig.1), In the lay-up $[0/90]_{4s}$ laminates, the 0° oriented fibers (57% of the plies) bear the load and the laminates responses are dominated by the behavior of these 0° fibers, resulting in a behavior independent of temperature. This is the reason why the laminate behavior is almost elastic-brittle despite the ductile behavior of the matrix. Then this slightly nonlinear behavior is not associated with a plastic behavior of the PPS matrix but to the gradual failure of 0° -oriented fibers during loading. It is consistent with the literature results because the maximum test temperature is higher than the glass transition temperature ($T_g=98^\circ\text{C}$) of C/PPS composites around which the ductile behavior of the PPS matrix is magnified. However, the laminate's fiber-dominated behavior is not significantly influenced by the matrix response at elevated temperature.

FIGURE 1 the tensile σ - ϵ curve of C/PPS at different temperature **FIGURE 2** changes in tensile property with increasing temperature in C/PPS laminates

Considering the mechanical properties of C/PPS laminates, temperature seems to influence very little both strength and stiffness with relative changes ranging from -3% to -7%. Thus, a service temperature equal to 120°C is not significantly detrimental for the mechanical behavior of C/PPS laminates subjected to such loadings.

FIGURE 3 SEM observations after failure of the tensile samples (a):RT; (b): 120°C .

3.2 Compressive test

The laminates stacking sequence for compressive tests is $[0/90]_{4s}$ what is approximately equivalent to $[0]_8$ layup because the reinforcement fabric is balanced in the weft and warp directions. The compressive tests require the use of a specific fixture preventing specimen's buckling. Throughout the operating temperature range (ambient to 120°C) failure was brittle and via the formation of a through-thickness shear-fault consisting of sheared fiber bundles. The compressive strength exhibits a significant decline with temperature (see Fig 5). Around the glass transition temperature of C/PPS laminates, failure was dominated by kink-band formation at significantly reduced failure stress. This transition in failure appeared to be caused by the reduction in the PPS ultimate compression stress,

which is commonly obtained from relation $\sigma_{comp} = F^u / t \cdot w$. This strength is significantly affected by a temperature increase up to 120°C because it decreased by 25% (see Fig.5).

FIGURE 4 the compressive σ - ε curve of C/PPS laminates at different temperature

FIGURE 5 changes in compressive property with increasing temperature in C/PPS laminates

SEM observations indication that, at temperatures lower than the glass transition temperature T_g , shear cracking and delamination predominate (see Fig.6). Around and higher than T_g , the failure is characterized by kinking and fracture of fiber bundles (as it is indicated by the dotted line on SEM views). In accordance with Grape and Gupta, experiments at elevated temperatures indicate the dominating failure mechanism to be localized yielding, of the matrix, triggered by the out-of-plane deformation of the load-aligned bundles at the crimp. This localized yielding initiates shear failure, which leads to fracture and crushing of the fibers within the cross-ply, which upon reaching the already compressed load-aligned bundles leads to micro buckling of the individual fibers. The failure was rather catastrophic and directly associated with a micro buckling-induced crushing of the axial fibers happening very close to the peak stress. At temperatures higher than the glass transition temperature, the failure mode is more consistent with plastic buckling.

FIGURE 6 SEM observations after failure of the compressive samples (a):RT; (b):120°C.

3.3 Flexural test

This test is widely used because of its simplicity, but this configuration does not lead to a pure stress state within the tested specimens. Tensile and compressive stresses are highest are maximum along it neutral axis. Thus, the span-to-thickness ratio (L/t) can be calibrated to promote different failure modes. The stress-stain curves exhibit a brittle failure at both temperature, but the nonlinear flexural response of the laminate at 120°C is mainly associated with plastic deformation of the matrix (see Fig.7). The laminate's stacking sequence is $[0/90]_{4s}$. Classical beam theory gives the maximum tensile σ^u (or compressive) and shear τ^u stresses due to flexural loading: $\sigma^u = 3F^m L / 2wt^2$ and $\tau^u = 3F^m / 4wt$, A temperature increase around the glass transition temperature of C/PPS seems to be detrimental for the flexural properties of this material because its strength decreased by 31% and its flexural stiffness by 15%.(see Fig.8)

FIGURE 7 the deflection-load curve of C/PPS laminates at different temperature **FIGURE 8** changes in flexural property with increasing temperature in C/PPS laminates

The SEM observations provide information about the specific damage mechanisms taking place within the laminate that result in changes in mechanical properties. Considering the elevated span-to-thickness ratio ($L/t=16$) used in these tests, the normal stress σ is prominent in relation to the shear τ resulting in a failure of the laminate by tension or compression in the outer plies. At RT, a few inter laminar cracks can be observed around the neutral axis and can be explain by the local debonding of the fiber matrix interface (see Fig.9(a)). At 120°C, the enhanced plasticization of the matrix occurs during the load transfer between the plies and dissipates a part of the mechanical transmitted to the sample (see Fig.9(b)). Consequently, this plasticity mechanism prevents other failure mechanisms from happening and the sample finally seems to fail in compression in the contact area with the upper anvil. This changes in damage mechanism with increasing temperature can be considered from the laminate microstructure point of view. It turns out that the fabric reinforcement gives the laminate a structure where the weave layer consists of different areas that are rich either in fibers or in matrix. It is instrumental in slowing down the propagation of both inter laminar and intra laminar cracks and in promoting propagation of the cracks along the five-harness satin weave.

FIGURE 9 SEM observations after failure of the flexural samples (a):RT; (b):120°C.

4 CONCLUSIONS

This paper aimed at investigating the influence of temperature on the mechanical behavior of carbon fiber fabric reinforced PPS laminates subjected to various stress states at different temperatures (room temperature and 120°C): tensile, compressive tests and flexural tests. About the tensile properties of C/PPS laminates, a service temperature higher than the glass transition temperature of C/PPS composites (i.e., $T_g = 98^\circ\text{C}$) seems to influence very little both strength and stiffness of thermoplastic laminates, whereas it strongly depreciates the compressive and flexural properties of C/PPS laminates. The strength and modulus decrease with the ductile behavior exacerbated at high temperature because it more or less extended plasticization of the PPS matrix according to the laminate layup. A temperature increase

around the glass transition temperature of C/PPS composite materials degrades significantly the already weak quality of the adhesion at the fiber/matrix interface. The ductile behavior of the matrix enhanced by elevated temperatures seems to be detrimental for the compressive strength, the flexural properties.

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